

Soft Skills and Resilience of Cooperatives : Toward a Transformation Inspired by South Korea.

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Résumé :

La gestion des coopératives, bien que fondamentale, est souvent sous-estimée dans les analyses économiques et sociales. Si des valeurs telles que la solidarité et la démocratie sont cruciales pour les coopératives, elles ne suffisent pas à garantir une résilience face aux défis. La résilience des coopératives repose également sur le savoir-être, qui inclut des compétences interpersonnelles et éthiques telles que la communication, l'empathie et le leadership collaboratif. Ces compétences sont essentielles pour créer un environnement de travail harmonieux et favoriser la pérennité des coopératives dans un contexte économique et social en constante évolution. L'article présente une **partie théorique** consacrée à la résilience des coopératives, en mettant en lumière l'importance du savoir-être comme levier fondamental pour renforcer leur capacité d'adaptation. Il analyse ensuite le **modèle sud-coréen** comme une source d'inspiration pertinente, en soulignant l'intérêt de pratiques managériales axées sur la communication transparente, le leadership partagé et l'engagement communautaire. Ce modèle, fondé sur la valorisation des compétences humaines, montre comment une gouvernance coopérative plus participative et relationnelle peut renforcer la résilience. La recherche s'appuie sur une approche hypothético-déductive appliquée à la région de **Kénitra-Sidi Kacem-Sidi Slimane**, afin d'évaluer les facteurs qui freinent ou favorisent la résilience des coopératives marocaines. L'étude conclut que le développement du savoir-être, à travers des pratiques inspirées du modèle sud-coréen, est essentiel pour garantir la résilience et la durabilité des coopératives marocaines. Ainsi, une gouvernance plus participative et humaine constitue la principale voie pour relever les défis auxquels ces organisations sont confrontées.

Mots-clés :

Gestion des coopératives, Résilience, Savoir-être, Compétences interpersonnelles, Leadership collaboratif, Communication, Empathie, Coopératives marocaines, Modèle sud-coréen, Transformation durable, Défis sociaux, Compétences éthiques.

Abstract :

The management of cooperatives, although fundamental, is often underestimated in economic and social analyses. While values such as solidarity and democracy are crucial for cooperatives, they are not sufficient to ensure resilience in the face of challenges. The resilience of cooperatives also depends on *soft skills*, which include interpersonal and ethical competencies such as communication, empathy, and collaborative leadership. These skills are essential for creating a harmonious work environment and supporting the long-term sustainability of cooperatives in a constantly evolving socio-economic context. The article presents a theoretical section dedicated to the resilience of cooperatives, highlighting the importance of soft skills as a key lever to strengthen their adaptive capacity. It then examines the South Korean model as a relevant source of inspiration, emphasizing the value of management practices based on transparent communication, shared leadership, and community engagement. This model, centered on the enhancement of human competencies, demonstrates how a more participatory and relational cooperative governance can reinforce resilience. The research adopts a hypothetico-deductive approach applied to the Kénitra-Sidi Kacem-Sidi Slimane region in order to evaluate the factors that hinder or support the resilience of Moroccan cooperatives.

The study concludes that developing soft skills through practices inspired by the South Korean model is essential to ensure the resilience and sustainability of Moroccan **cooperatives**. Thus, a more participatory and human-centered governance emerges as the main path to overcoming the challenges faced by these organizations.

Keywords:

Cooperative management, Resilience, Soft skills, Interpersonal competencies, Collaborative leadership, Communication, Empathy, Moroccan cooperatives, South Korean model, Sustainable transformation, Social challenges, Ethical competencies.

Summary :

Cooperative management represents a fundamental pillar for economic and social development, particularly in contexts where communities seek to strengthen their autonomy and resilience in the face of contemporary challenges. However, cooperative management, although recognized as a strategic lever, is often underestimated in economic and social analyses. Traditionally, cooperatives are perceived through values such as solidarity, democracy, and collective management. However, these principles, while crucial for their proper functioning, do not automatically guarantee their resilience in the face of the many difficulties that may arise, whether economic, social, or environmental. One of the key factors often missing in the analysis of cooperative management is interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills refer to a set of interpersonal and ethical skills such as communication, empathy, active listening, and collaborative leadership. These skills are essential for creating a harmonious work environment and strengthening relationships within cooperative teams. In a constantly changing world, where challenges are multiple and complex, the world has experienced several crises : economic, health, social, environmental, and political. In this context, the ability to resist has become a necessity for the survival of organizations. Today, every organization is obliged to face a major challenge, namely the environment, which has become turbulent (Emery & Trist, 1965). There is practically no consolidated literature on "cooperative resilience." Cooperative resilience is a long-term process, based on reflexivity and interactions between members, leaders and national and international organizations (Borda-Rodriguez & Vicari, 2014). The resilience of cooperatives depends as much on their ability to manage their human resources and internal relationships as on the management of material or financial resources. Soft skills, as a key skill, play a crucial role in creating positive team dynamics, which in turn supports the sustainable performance of cooperatives. The importance of soft skills for cooperative resilience has been widely recognized in many parts of the world. South Korea, in particular, has implemented a cooperative model that integrates these human and relational skills, thus enabling more fluid, transparent, and collaborative management. The South Korean model is distinguished by its approach focused on transparent communication, shared leadership, and strong community engagement, elements that strengthen cohesion within cooperatives and their ability to overcome challenges. These practices, based on soft skills principles, have enabled South Korean cooperatives to remain resilient despite economic crises and social transformations. In this context, it is relevant to look at the situation of Moroccan cooperatives, particularly those located in the region of Kénitra-Sidi Kacem-Sidi Slimane, to assess their

resilience in the face of the challenges they face. Indeed, although Moroccan cooperatives have experienced significant growth in recent years, they often remain vulnerable due to certain shortcomings in human resource management, particularly with regard to the interpersonal and ethical skills needed to ensure stable and effective internal dynamics. The absence of skills such as collaborative leadership or fluid communication can hamper their effectiveness and their ability to adapt to an unstable socio-economic environment. In order to explore ways to strengthen the resilience of these cooperatives, this research adopts a hypothetico-deductive approach within the framework of a positivist approach, aiming to identify and analyze the factors that influence this resilience. The objective is to determine to what extent the model of South Korean cooperatives, which values interpersonal skills and human and relational skills, could inspire and improve the management and resilience of Moroccan cooperatives. By drawing on proven and innovative practices, this study aims to offer concrete avenues to strengthen the sustainability of cooperatives in the region studied. Thus, this research explores not only the theory of resilience applied to cooperatives, but also the practical and contextual aspects that make it possible to overcome the obstacles that stand in the way of these structures. It highlights the importance of integrating human skills into the management of cooperatives to promote their growth and sustainable development. Through this reflection, the objective is to open up perspectives for a sustainable transformation of Moroccan cooperatives, inspired by good South Korean practices and adapted to local reality.

1. Literature review

Today, soft skills are emerging as a determining factor in the quality and effectiveness of decision-making and management processes. While traditional management focuses primarily on the structures, policies, and rules that govern institutions, soft skills refer to the human and relational skills essential for meeting governance challenges, particularly in a context marked by diversity, complexity, and globalization.

1.1 Conceptualization of knowing how to be

Soft skills differ from hard skills in that they are often intangible and difficult to measure. However, numerous studies show that people with strong behavioral skills are better able to manage complex situations, collaborate effectively with others, and adapt to change. Furthermore, these skills are crucial for personal development, as they promote better emotional management, greater resilience in the face of stress, and an increased ability to understand and respect cultural differences. Soft skills play a key role in cooperative governance. They represent emotional competencies. These qualities are essential for creating an environment

where members feel listened to. Developed soft skills help improve interactions, resolve conflicts constructively, and foster team spirit."Emotion, catalyst of interpersonal skills" (Henri Boudreault Ph. D., 2015) The author clearly emphasized that emotion is a fundamental element in the concept of interpersonal skills, which he considers essential in learning. Emotion was not chosen, but rather imposed itself as necessary in his model. It plays a key role in motivation and learning in general, but in the case of interpersonal skills, it becomes a learning object in itself. Indeed, emotion directly impacts the learner's behavior.

Knowledge is associated with technology and science, while know-how refers to specific methods and practices. On the other hand, know-how depends on an individual's action according to the situation in which he finds himself, according to his emotions, beliefs and personal evaluations of what is fair or unfair. In a detailed way, know-how is thus defined as the communication activity of users/learners is not only affected by their knowledge, understanding and skills but also by personal factors related to their own personality and characterized by attitudes, motivations, values, beliefs, cognitive styles and personality types that constitute their identity. (Carlo, 2013) HENRI BOUDREAUULT emphasizes the importance of developing didactic situations that allow the learner to understand the distance between his spontaneous emotions and his conscious emotions. He notes that most training environments are not adapted to foster the development of professional know-how and calls for rethinking teaching methods to address this new field. In a cooperative, governance is based on principles of participation, transparency, and collective responsibility, which can be strongly influenced by members' interpersonal skills. Interpersonal skills, as described by the author, include the management of emotions and how they impact individual behaviors in a collective environment. Thus, emotion plays a crucial role in how members interact, make decisions, and manage conflicts within the cooperative. Furthermore, cooperative governance encourages a culture of responsibility and commitment. Members are not only stakeholders in decision-making, but also partners in implementing the decided actions. This creates a sense of belonging and ownership that is fundamental to the long-term success of cooperatives. Cooperative governance, combined with strengthened interpersonal skills, helps build strong relationships between members, thus fostering positive and sustainable dynamics. Cultivating these human values is essential to ensuring not only the economic viability but also the social impact of cooperatives. Frédéric Faure, in his work on interpersonal skills, highlights the importance of this set of interpersonal and behavioral skills in professional environments. Interpersonal skills are a set of behaviors, attitudes, and values that facilitate interpersonal relationships in a

professional environment. It includes qualities such as active listening, the ability to collaborate, empathy, conflict management, effective communication, and respect for others (Faure & Cucchi, 2020). Interpersonal skills are essential for improving cooperation, strengthening team resilience, and fostering humane and effective governance. In cooperatives, as in other types of organizations, they are therefore crucial for strengthening the cohesion and commitment of members, particularly in times of crisis or transformation

1.2 The conceptualization of knowledge within cooperatives in South Korea

Soft **skills** in the context of **cooperatives** in South Korea go beyond mere technical or professional skills. They are a set of values, behaviors, and social norms rooted in Korean culture that guide human interactions and govern relationships between members of a cooperative organization. These values directly influence how cooperatives operate, particularly in terms of **social cohesion, solidarity, and** and of **resilience**.

1.2.1 Cultural Know-How : The Jeong

Cultural roots play a key role in the development of cooperatives and social economy initiatives, particularly in South Korea. In this context, deep values such as solidarity and cooperation, derived from cultural traditions, are at the heart of collective practices that foster the resilience of cooperatives. According to (Sung Ai Lee and Hervé Defalvard 2019), The importance of cultural anchoring in South Korean cooperatives cannot be underestimated, as it directs social and organizational dynamics towards common goals, thus consolidating the effectiveness and sustainability of these structures. In South Korean cooperatives, a fundamental value that guides interactions and decision-making is collective solidarity. Members share not only economic interests but also a common vision based on principles of social justice, reciprocity, and mutual support. This vision is in perfect harmony with the spirit of jeong, a central concept of Korean culture, as defined by (Inju Yang 2006). Jeong represents a deep emotional bond, a form of solidarity that goes beyond simple contractual relationships, fostering lasting solidarity and harmonious cooperation among members. This emotional connection, embodied by jeong, is particularly visible in the way Korean cooperatives operate. They favor collective leadership largely inspired by the values of jeong. This leadership model is based on the idea that shared management and the active involvement of each member strengthen individual autonomy while creating effective collective dynamics. Inclusiveness and member empowerment are at the heart of this leadership, allowing everyone to play an active role in managing the organization. In this participatory governance system, jeong helps balance hierarchical relationships by creating an environment of mutual trust and respect. While hierarchy remains present, it is tempered by

the prevailing spirit of solidarity and goodwill, creating a more harmonious structure less marked by conflict. This model allows cooperatives to maintain strong internal cohesion, strengthening their resilience in the face of economic and social challenges, whether related to market volatility, economic crises, or other external factors. In short, embedding cultural values such as solidarity, cooperation, and jeong in the governance model of South Korean cooperatives is a key factor in their development and resilience. These values not only improve organizational efficiency, but also strengthen the bond between members, encourage collective decision-making, and foster a collective response to the challenges of the economic environment. Participatory management and collective leadership, supported by the spirit of jeong, ensure the sustainability of these cooperatives while preserving a strong and supportive social fabric.

1.2.2 Organizational Resilience and Collective Leadership in Korean Cooperatives

Social skills in Korean cooperatives are not limited to interpersonal relationships but also play a fundamental role in the structuring and functioning of collective leadership. The latter is defined as the ability to influence and mobilize members around common goals, emphasizing participation, transparency, and collaboration. This management style is essential to ensure the resilience of cooperatives. (R. Dayanandan and Roba Huka 2019) In this context, jeong practices, which denote a deep emotional connection and solidarity among members, directly shape how these organizations handle challenges and decisions. In many South Korean cooperatives, the leadership model is based on a participatory and collaborative approach. Unlike more hierarchical leadership models, where a central authority holds decision-making power, Korean cooperatives favor collective leadership, in which decisions are made in consultation with all members. This is based on the idea that cooperation and solidarity between individuals are key elements of collective success.

1.3 The conceptualization of resilience :

The concept of resilience reflects the ability to resist shocks and crises, the word resilience according to Robert is "the ability to overcome traumatic shocks. Ecology Capacity (of an ecosystem, a species) to return to a state of equilibrium after an exceptional event." Organizational resilience is the ability of an organization to put in place a set of dynamic factors in order to adapt to shocks, mitigate their effects and cope with the consequences while simultaneously taking advantage of emerging opportunities from a crisis (Mamouni Linnios & Mazzarol, 2011). Organizational resilience is more like the ability to overcome a clear danger. To address this danger, K. Burnad and R. Bhamra highlighted the mechanisms that contribute

to strengthening organizational resilience by improving situational awareness, reducing organizational vulnerabilities to systemic risk, and restoring effectiveness after a shock or disruption. (Burnard & Bhamra, 2011). Henri aptly defined organizational resilience as the ability of an organization to adapt, reorganize, and renew itself in the face of disruptive events while maintaining its long-term objectives. This ability to bounce back from crises or major changes involves not only overcoming immediate obstacles, but also preparing for future situations by integrating prevention and learning mechanisms. For Boudreault, organizational resilience is not limited to crisis response, but also includes adaptability.

2. Research Methodology : Epistemological Framework and Reasoning Strategy

In this research, the adopted methodological approach is grounded in a pragmatist epistemological framework, which posits that knowledge is constructed through the interaction between the researcher and the field of study, with particular attention paid to the practical application of the results obtained. According to Dewey (1938), pragmatism rests on the idea that truth emerges from experimentation and experience, rather than from a theoretical hypothesis detached from reality.

In this context, we adopt an inductive approach, exploring social phenomena through direct observations, interviews, and surveys in order to generate hypotheses about the dynamics of cooperative management and interpersonal skills. The reasoning approach is primarily hypothetico-deductive, where working hypotheses are formulated based on existing theories and preliminary observations. These hypotheses are then tested through empirical methods to confirm or refute the proposed relationships between interpersonal skills and cooperative governance.

This approach allows for a rigorous response to the research questions by identifying causal links and evaluating the impact of interpersonal skills on cooperative management and their resilience.

3. Context and objective of the research :

Cooperatives in Morocco, particularly those in the agricultural sector, are a fundamental element of the rural economy. They allow farmers to pool their resources to improve their production and profitability. However, these cooperatives face challenges such as internal tensions, poor communication between members, and a lack of coordination in decision-making. The objective of this study is to analyze the impact of interpersonal skills on the governance of Moroccan cooperatives. The question that arises is : Does interpersonal skills help strengthen governance principles (transparency, accountability, participation) ? How does

mastering interpersonal skills influence group dynamics and the success of projects within a cooperative ? Our objective is to assess whether improving interpersonal skills contributes to better decision-making and more inclusive and transparent management. Thus, measuring the impact of good governance on the collaboration and performance of cooperative members is to answer the following question : Does good governance promote a more collaborative and productive working environment ?

4. Elements of observation of know-how : comparative and contextualized approach

Before analyzing interpersonal skills and their impact on the resilience of agricultural cooperatives, it is essential to understand the structural and socioeconomic context in which these cooperatives operate. Data provided by the Office for the Development of Cooperation (ODCO) provides a quantitative overview of the distribution, areas of activity, and dynamics of cooperative creation in the regions of Kenitra, Sidi Kacem, and Sidi Slimane. This information will help us better situate our study and target territorial specificities.

4.1 Statistical overview of agricultural cooperatives in the provinces of Kenitra, Sidi Kacem and Sidi Slimane

The following table presents the figures provided by the Office for the Development of Cooperation (ODCO) for 2022 concerning agricultural cooperatives operating in the provinces of Kenitra, Sidi Kacem, and Sidi Slimane. These data provide a quantitative overview of the cooperative fabric in these areas, with a view to better contextualizing our analysis of interpersonal skills.

Table No. 1 : Number of agricultural cooperatives and members by province (ODCO, 2024)

Province	Number of cooperatives	Number of members
Kenitra	918	17950
Sidi Slimane	734	7464
Sidi Kacem	838	9354

Source : Office for Development and Cooperation (ODCO), 2024 data

Analyzing the evolution of the cooperative network in the provinces of Kenitra, Sidi Kacem, and Sidi Slimane provides a better understanding of local dynamics in terms of solidarity-based agricultural development. This data, taken from the annual reports of the Office for the Development of Cooperation (ODCO), demonstrates a significant growth in the number of cooperatives over the period 2020–2024. This report was provided to me by the ODCO, in the form of an external document, which guarantees its reliability and timeliness. To better

visualize this evolution, the following table presents a summary of the number of cooperatives registered in each province over these five years.

Table 2 : Evolution of the number of agricultural cooperatives by province (2020–2024)

Province	Kenitra	Sidi Slimane	Sidi Kacem
2020	607	521	544
2021	754	608	604
2022	814	690	684
2023	883	779	706
2024	918	734	838

Source : ODCO, (external document), 2024.

Verify the impact of **interpersonal skills** on the **resilience of agricultural cooperatives in the Kenitra region, Sidi Kacem, and Sidi Slimane** requires a structured methodological approach that combines both qualitative (semi-directive interviews) and quantitative (questionnaire) analyses in order to assess whether relational skills in the management of a cooperative effectively influence its ability to face challenges. We will then set up several indicators to quantitatively evaluate the know-how through this table which represents the aspects of relational management, internal communication, teamwork, and conflict management within the cooperatives. In this following table we will see the indicators for evaluating the know-how of agricultural cooperatives :

Table No. 3 : Interview grid according to aspects, indicators and objectives

The aspects	The indicators	Measureme Method	Objective
Internal Communication	Frequency of coordination meetings	Number of meetings per month/quarter	A high number of meetings indicates smooth communication among members.
	Member participation rate	Percentage of members attending meetings	A high participation rate reflects member engagement and good communication.
	Assessment of information transparency	Number of important decisions communicated	The more shared decisions there are, the higher the transparency.
Teamwork and Collaboration	Cooperation Index	Number of important decisions communicated	The more shared decisions there are, the higher the transparency.

	Conflict resolution rate	Number of collective activities carried out (per month/quarter)	A high number of group activities reflects good collaboration between members.
	Feedback on team spirit	Satisfaction survey (scale 1 to 5)	A high score in this survey shows good team dynamics and positive interpersonal skills.
Leadership and Decision Making	Shared leadership rate	Number of leaders involved in decisions	Collective leadership indicates democratic and participatory know-how.
	Evaluation of decision making	Proportion of decisions made collectively vs. Centrally	A high proportion of collective decisions indicates good participatory and collaborative management.
Training and Skills	Continuing education rate	Percentage of members trained in relational skills	A high rate of continuing education shows an investment in developing members' knowledge.
	Frequency of skill-building workshops	Number of workshops on interpersonal skills	The more workshops on conflict management and communication, the more relational skills are strengthened.
Satisfaction and Engagement	Member satisfaction rate	Satisfaction survey on the atmosphere and internal relations (scale 1 to 5)	A high satisfaction rate reflects a positive working environment and strong interpersonal skills within the cooperative.
	Member retention rate	Percentage of members remaining from one year to the next	A high retention rate shows that members are engaged and find a collaborative and harmonious atmosphere.
Conflict Management and Social Climate	Rate of peaceful conflict management	Number of conflicts resolved peacefully	A high rate of peaceful conflict management reflects strong skills in dispute management.
	Social climate within the cooperative	Social climate survey (scale 1 to 5)	A positive social climate indicates a harmonious atmosphere, which demonstrates strong interpersonal skills within the cooperative.

Source : the author

4.2 The South Korean experience as a lever of inspiration

Cooperatives in South **Korea** have emerged as a key sector in the country's economic and social development, particularly in the agricultural, social, and consumer sectors. Since the 1990s, Korea has gradually strengthened the legislative and financial infrastructure to support the social economy, an approach that combines economic and social objectives. (KoSEA Report, December 2019) **Cooperatives** in Korea play a fundamental role in reducing social inequality, creating jobs, and improving citizens' quality of life, while supporting vulnerable populations and fostering **community solidarity**. A central concept underlying this cooperative dynamic is **jeong**, a Korean term that is difficult to translate precisely but represents a **deep emotional attachment**, a **sense of solidarity** and **caring** between individuals. **Jeong** is deeply rooted in Korean culture and is seen as a pillar of interpersonal and community relationships. It goes beyond simple contractual exchanges, creating lasting bonds based on trust, respect, and empathy. Jeong is described as affection or a feeling of empathy toward others, shared and experienced between two or more people, and constitutes a fundamental subset of the psychosocial characteristics of human relationships in South Korea.

Jeong is described as affection or a feeling of empathy toward others, shared and experienced between two or more people, and constitutes a fundamental subset of the psychosocial characteristics of human relationships in South Korea. This emotional bond directly influences how members of Korean cooperatives interact, cooperate, and assist each other in collective projects. (Inju Yang; 2006) Cooperatives in South Korea are also spaces for education and training for their members, which also reflects a dimension of personal development and soft skills. This includes training on collaborative skills that answers the following question : How to work effectively in a team and manage conflicts in a cooperative environment ? As well as training on the work ethic that emphasizes the values of social responsibility, professional ethics and contribution to collective well-being.

4.3 The factors of know-how in Korean cooperatives

In this study, we explored dimensions of interpersonal skills, drawing inspiration from certain cultural references from the Korean model, particularly in terms of interpersonal relationships and social cohesion. Two fundamental concepts emerge in particular : **jeong**, which embodies a form of deep emotional attachment between individuals, and **cheong**, which represents a form of socio-emotional regulation in daily interactions. These notions shed light on certain dynamics of cooperation, mutual respect and conflict management, which can enrich our understanding of interpersonal skills in a cooperative framework.

Table 4 : The Factors of Soft Skills and their Definition according to the Authors

The factors of knowing how to be	Definition	AUTHORS
Social harmony	The Concept of " Jeong" is a deep feeling of affection and interpersonal connection . It is not a superficial or fleeting love, but a deep attachment and lasting that is built over time. Jeong plays a crucial role in family and social relationships in Korea, and it is an emotion that strengthens bonds between individuals.	Irene J. Kim (2006)
The notion of "face" (cheong)	Cheong functions as a "socio-emotional grammar" in Korean interpersonal relationships, influencing how individuals interact and establish emotional bonds. It is emphasized that cheong is an interpersonal emotion, manifesting in relationships rather than in the individual alone.	(Sang Chin Choi and Soo Hyang Choi 2001)

Source : the author

The concepts of **Jeong** and **Cheong**, derived from Korean culture, play a vital role in managing interpersonal relationships within cooperatives. **Jeong**, by strengthening lasting emotional bonds between members, and **Cheong**, by regulating emotions in interactions, are key factors in maintaining social harmony and cohesion within groups. These dimensions of interpersonal skills are crucial for the **resilience of agricultural cooperatives**, as they promote solidarity, effective cooperation, and conflict management, which are essential elements for addressing economic and social challenges. Integrating these concepts into the operations of cooperatives can thus strengthen their ability to overcome difficulties and persist in a complex environment.

5. Discussions of hypotheses and results :

The results presented in this study are taken from a questionnaire I distributed to around fifty cooperatives located in the regions of Kenitra, Sidi Kacem, and Sidi Slimane. Among the open-ended questions in the questionnaire, one asked about suggestions for improving interpersonal skills within cooperatives. Here are some relevant responses : "Yes, I suggest organizing interpersonal communication and conflict management workshops to strengthen cohesion

among members. It would also be beneficial to establish regular meetings where everyone can express themselves freely and be listened to with respect. Promoting respect, caring communication, and recognition among members would help strengthen interpersonal skills within the cooperative." These suggestions highlight the importance of initiatives aimed at improving communication and interpersonal relationships within cooperatives. Establishing such workshops and discussion spaces could significantly strengthen the **resilience** of cooperatives by fostering more harmonious relationships and better conflict management. These practices are in line with **Jeong is concepts**. And **Cheong**, which value social harmony and emotional regulation in interactions, crucial elements for the sustainability and cohesion of groups. These suggestions highlight the importance of initiatives to improve **communication** and **interpersonal relationships**. Within cooperatives. The establishment of workshops and exchange spaces would strengthen the **resilience** of cooperatives by promoting harmonious relationships and better conflict management. These practices are in line with the concepts of **Jeong** and **Cheong**, essential for the cohesion and sustainability of groups. Communication in a cooperative is a key element in the flow of ideas, problem solving, and identifying needs. However, this communication requires a whole package of elements such as the ability to listen actively, understand emotions, and respond appropriately. Daniel Goulemen emphasized communication as a key element, and he said that those who communicate best achieve better results and progress more quickly. (Boussuat et al. 2017). Among the responses obtained in the questionnaire, certain negative dynamics within the cooperatives were highlighted. In fact, inappropriate interpersonal behaviors, such as frequent interruptions by some members, failure to consider divergent opinions, or a lack of interest in the ideas of others, were reported. Furthermore, interactions marked by impolite or condescending language, both during meetings and in daily exchanges, were mentioned as factors detrimental to the work atmosphere and collaboration within the organization.

5.1 Analysis of the Impact of Interpersonal Skills and the Integration of Jeong and Cheong Concepts in Cooperatives

Interpersonal skills play a crucial role in the management of cooperatives, and the integration of the principles of **Jeong** and **Cheong** can significantly enhance internal dynamics, governance, and overall performance. These elements help create a more harmonious, productive, and resilient working environment, conducive to cooperation and long-term success.

The table below presents the impact of interpersonal skills on cooperative management :

Table 5 : Effects of Interpersonal Skills and the Application of Jeong and Cheong on Cooperative Functioning

Element	Impact on Cooperatives	Jeong	Cheong
Interpersonal Skills	Strengthens cooperation and harmonious relationships.	Strong bond between members.	Mutual support.
Communication	Improves transparency and collaboration.	Smooth communication.	Open exchanges.
Conflict Management	Reduces tension and promotes a positive environment.	Harmonious resolution.	Collective conflict management.
Team Cohesion	Strengthens commitment and solidarity.	Strong unity.	Mutual commitment.
Governance	Facilitates transparent and fair decision-making.	Collective decisions.	Participatory governance.
Performance	Improves resilience and productivity	Sustainability of cooperation.	Sustainability and competitiveness.

Source : the author

5.2 Schematization of the Results in our Sample : Influence of the Concepts of *Jeong* and *Cheong* on the Social Dynamics of the Study Region

In this analysis, we add the dimension of interpersonal skills and its link to the functioning of cooperatives within the region studied. Interpersonal skills, which include qualities such as respect, listening, and the ability to work together, are essential for maintaining harmonious relationships and fostering cooperation. Cooperatives, which are based on principles of solidarity and collective work, are an ideal setting for observing the impact of jeong and cheong. These concepts help highlight how emotional bonds and mutual commitment can strengthen team cohesion and improve the effectiveness of cooperative governance. They thus provide a relevant framework for understanding the importance of human relationships in the success, resilience, and sustainability of cooperatives

Figure n°1 : Schematization of concepts Jeong and Cheong

Source : the author

Emotional attachment in a cooperative setting is not only beneficial for employee engagement and motivation, but also plays a central role in strengthening cohesion and solidarity within the organization. Employees who feel valued for their personal and professional contributions, and who are emotionally connected to their work environment, are more likely to invest their efforts in achieving collective goals. This dynamic creates a climate of trust, where collaboration and innovation are encouraged, and where each individual feels both responsible and supported. This allows the cooperative to grow sustainably, building strong relationships and fostering a harmonious and productive work environment. Thus, by cultivating genuine emotional attachment, cooperatives can not only improve their internal performance but also play a key role in local economic and social development, embodying values of solidarity and shared well-being.

Conclusion

In conclusion, it is worth noting that a cooperative's performance is linked to the presence of interpersonal skills, especially within an organizational model based on cooperation and member engagement. However, it is essential to understand that interpersonal skills, while essential, are only one factor among others that influence a cooperative's organizational and social performance. Integrating interpersonal skills with good governance can effectively create a beneficial synergy for the cooperative. Interpersonal skills promote harmonious and respectful relationships, while good governance ensures that decisions are made in a transparent, fair, and accountable manner. Together, these two elements can significantly improve communication, collaboration, and the performance of Moroccan cooperatives. By combining these approaches, cooperatives can not only achieve their economic objectives but also strengthen the trust and involvement of members, thus ensuring sustainable and harmonious development.

Thus, in order to succeed and thrive in the long term, cooperatives must prioritize the improvement of human and relational skills, while strengthening governance for a more solid and cooperative future. In the context of this research, training sessions on soft skills will be organized in the regions of Sidi Kacem, Sidi Slimane, and Kénitra to strengthen the interpersonal skills of the members of local cooperatives. These trainings will aim to promote communication, conflict management, and team cohesion, which are essential elements for improving the management of cooperatives. The results of these initiatives will be analyzed and presented in a subsequent article, where we will detail the observed impacts and lessons learned from the practical application of these training sessions in the field.

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